

Supplementary Material

Over four months of ethylene production: Unlocking the potential of solid-state photosynthetic cell factories

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Supplementary Figure 1. Validation of *efe* gene integrity during long-term cultivation of ethylene-producing *Synechocystis* cells entrapped within thin nanocellulose films compared to suspension culture.

Representative segment of the alignment:

Sequencing analysis of the *efe* gene from *Pseudomonas syringae* confirms the genetic stability of the plasmid under different cultivation conditions. The samples were collected at different time points. The reference sequence (#1) corresponds to the *efe* gene from *P. syringae*. Experimental samples included:

- #2 Film at the start of the experiment;
- #3 Film after 142 days of cultivation (see Figure 1C in the main text);
- #4 Film after 43 days under 120 mM bicarbonate supplementation (see Figure 2A);
- #5 Suspension culture from the PhBFR at the end of the experiment (see Figure 3).

Supplementary Figure 2. Daily ethylene production during long-term cultivation of the *Synechocystis* efe suspension culture. The PhBFR was operated under conditions comparable to those shown in Figure 3 of the main text. Addition of 1 mM IPTG on day 27 (arrow) resulted in a partial recovery of ethylene production.

Supplementary Figure 3. Daily changes in chlorophyll a content in the Ca^{2+} -PVA-TCNF film during long-term cultivation. The PhBFR was operated under continuous flow of BG11 medium (20 mL h^{-1}) supplemented with 20 mM sodium bicarbonate and a constant air supply (10 mL min^{-1}). IPTG (1 mM) was introduced into the bioreactor at the beginning of the experiment.

